

MAGNETOENCEPHALOGRAPHIC DATA INDICATES SEPARATE COMPONENT MODELING
IS NECESSARY IN EVALUATING EVOKED RESPONSES

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ABSTRACT

A double Gaussian Model was used to estimate dipole source contributions to magnetoencephalograms. The method was tested using four 2mm length dipoles fixed in conductive material enclosed within the human skull. Evoked responses were simulated by Gaussian activation of one dipole with a mean latency of 100ms, and a second dipole at 200ms. Simulations were performed over the left temporal bone and the occipital bone. Source contributions to each resultant waveform were estimated as the amplitude parameters of a best fit double Gaussian function. Comparing dipole inverse solutions from waveform peaks with those from estimated contributions revealed only a small difference in localization accuracy. Source strength is slightly better estimated using the component model method. The peak picking method overestimated strength when dipoles were aligned and underestimated when they were opposed.

INTRODUCTION

Our laboratory measures auditory and visual evoked responses to study the behavior of cognitive components under various workload conditions. A typical evoked field will have several components occurring after stimulus onset. Inverse solutions of various components typically localize the neural source contributing to the component at a unique location (1,2,3). The localization of a 100 ms auditory component has a different location from that of a 160 ms (3), and thus can not be modeled simply as a generator reversing polarity. In this paper, a Gaussian model is used to simulate many closely packed neurons being activated with distributed latencies. The model might be used to estimate neural sources' contributions to the components of the observed evoked response.

METHODS

Four current dipoles were constructed from 32 AWG single conductor shielded wire. The outer insulation and the shield were cut back to give a 2mm length between the exposed center conductor and

the shield. A small amount of solder was put on the ends of the dipole. Each dipole's center conductor simulates intracellular currents of many closely packed cortical neurons. The dipoles were positioned in a soft sponge, wrapped in chamois cloth, and soaked in a conductive electrode paste solution. This simulated brain and meninges material allowed the return currents to better approximate extracellular volume currents. Two dipoles were placed in the left temporal region to simulate auditory evoked responses (AER) and the other two were placed in the occipital region to simulate visual evoked responses (VER).

After enclosing the simulated brain within the skull, x-ray images were used to precisely locate the true dipole positions. An x-ray shot was taken parallel to each axis of a designated "head reference" coordinate system. The x-axis passes through skull landmarks just above the external ear orifices, the y-axis passes between the nasal bones, and the z-axis is the cross product of x and y. Because the x-ray procedure will produce an expanded image as a function of object position between the x-ray source and the film, a computer program was written to convert each dipole's image position to the head reference coordinate system.

Four stimulation conditions were performed in each of the two cranial regions. In the first, AERs were simulated by Gaussian activation of one temporal dipole with a mean latency of 100ms, and the other temporal dipole with a mean latency of 200ms. In the second, the polarity of the 200ms dipole was reversed, and in the third and fourth each dipole was solely activated. In all AER conditions, each dipole strength was 100nA-m. The magnetic field normal to the scalp surface was recorded at 50 positions with a 2nd order gradiometer coupled to a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID). All recordings were made within a two layer magnetically shielded chamber. The resultant waveforms were filtered with a passband of 0.3 to 30 Hz and at least 30 sweeps were averaged. The same conditions were repeated for the VER simulations in the occipital region with the exception that each VER dipole strength was 80nA-m.

Source contributions to each of the averaged sweeps in the first and second conditions were estimated as amplitude parameters of a best fit double Gaussian function. The fits were performed using a modified version of the subroutine curfit (4).

Fig. 1. Tracings of the x-ray images.

Fig. 2. Waveforms for the 4 conditions at an occipital location.

The skull's surface was digitized in 3-space at each measurement location using an instrumented arm apparatus with an accuracy of 3mm. A computer program transformed each surface location from the apparatus coordinate system to the head reference coordinate system.

The dipoles' locations were estimated by a least squares fit inverse solution. The fitting program uses a modified version of the subroutine curfit to fit the radial magnetic field data to a nonlinear function that models gradiometer detection of a dipole within a conducting sphere. The routine operates in a spherical coordinate system determined from the best fit sphere to the measurement positions on the skull. Dipole parameters are strength, range, elevation, azimuth, and orientation. At the conclusion of the fitting procedure, the resultant dipole parameters are transformed to the head reference coordinate system.

Dipole fits were generated for peak field amplitudes on all conditions, and for estimated source contributions on the first and second conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dipole positions and orientations are shown as tracings of the x-ray images in Figure 1. The V100 dipole is close and tangential to the surface. The V200 dipole is deep and primarily radial. The A100 dipole is deep and tangential. The A200 is deep and has a small radial component.

Four averaged waveforms were recorded at each measurement point. Figure 2 illustrates the temporal views for one point in the VER simulation. Note that the high pass filter response of the 100ms component will cause undesirable distortion of the 200ms component's data. The spatial views shown in Figure 3 illustrate the peak isofield contours for solely stimulated dipoles V100 and V200. The inverse solution dipole fits for the peak fields and the estimated contribution fields are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

The simulations illustrate some important characteristics of magnetoencephalography (MEG). As in all estimation procedures, an appropriate model is paramount. Although the magnetic field normal to the scalp is not significantly corrupted by volume currents or smeared by the various layers of the brain, skull, and scalp (5,6), a limiting factor of MEG is its inability to detect current sources oriented radially in a symmetrical

Condition	V100					V200				
	x	y	z	del	P	x	y	z	del	P
Known	-16	-53	24		80	-10	-34	42		80
V100	-14.3	-47.7	24.5	5.6	80.6	-1.7	-9.9	40.1	25.6	1863.1
V200										
V100+V200 PP	-15.0	-49.1	24.4	4.0	72.4	-1.5	-9.8	40.0	25.7	1873.5
V100+V200 BC	-15.9	-49.4	24.0	3.7	83.9	-1.5	-10.1	40.9	25.4	1866.4
V100-V200 PP	-15.1	-46.0	23.5	7.1	86.2	-0.9	-6.7	38.3	29.0	2920.1
V100-V200 BC	-18.6	-48.8	22.9	5.1	81.6	-0.7	-10.1	40.5	25.7	1550.1

Fig. 3. Contours for dipoles V100 and V200.

conductor. Because the V100 dipole is purely tangential and the occipital region is nearly spherical, the inverse solution model used is quite appropriate in estimating V100's location, strength, and orientation. The V100 data provides the best results for evaluating the component estimation method.

Although V100 and V200 stimulation means are temporally separated, the components overlap (Figure 2). The resultant component peaks are reduced or increased depending on positive or negative reinforcement at the measurement point. Since V100 and V200 contribute opposing fields over a large part of the measurement surface (Figure 3), most of the peaks are reduced in the V100+V200 condition and increased in the V100-V200 condition. The inverse solutions using data from a peak picker routine underestimate or overestimate the dipole strength for these respective conditions. Data from the double Gaussian routine accounted for the interference and better estimated V100 strength in both conditions (Table 1).

The encouraging results for dipole V100 were only achieved because the temporal Gaussian model and the spatial inverse solution model were appropriate. The other three dipoles all exhibited some deviation from the ideal source. Since the head is not a perfect sphere, a radially oriented source will produce an external field. However, present models can not handle this situation. Deep sources also present problems for MEG. The external field is reduced to zero as the source nears the center of a symmetrical conductor. Thus, inverse solutions for deep sources have difficulty converging with respect to the strength and range parameters. Although accurate localization may not be possible for the radial or the deep source, component estimation methods may be used to eliminate their interference on other components.

Component estimation yielded improvements in the inverse solution accuracy for a shallow tangential dipole in the occipital region. The method of component estimation could be improved by modeling all known contributors to the recorded data including any undesirable affects of a high pass filter response.

References

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